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PERSEUS

**2D Material-Based Multiple Oncotherapy
Against Metastatic Disease Using a
Radically New Computed Tomography
Approach**

DELIVERABLE

WP5 – D5.1 – Project Website

ABSTRACT

This document summarises the PERSEUS Website design and implementation, covering its sections, technical infrastructures, and related services.

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a summary of the work on the PERSEUS Website, its sections, technical infrastructures, and related services, while briefly referring to the project's logo and visual identity. It adheres to the PERSEUS DoA outlined in Work Package 5 - Communication & Dissemination, specifically addressing Task 5.2 Website design, execution, and upkeep.

This ensures a comprehensive reference for promoting PERSEUS's Web presence.

The document consists of four Chapters, an Executive Summary, Conclusions, and two Annexes.

Chapters 1, 2, and 3 present an overview of the PERSEUS Website layout and structure, technical infrastructure and tools, and its integration with social networks and additional services (e.g., Web feeds, analysis tools, etc.). Chapter 4 outlines the workflow of the Editorial Team and the content of the Website's various sections.

For the Graphic Identity study of PERSEUS, please refer to D5.2 - Project Logo

1 THE PERSEUS WEBSITE

The following domain has been registered for the project Website:

<http://www.perseusproject.eu>

The Website will function as the reference point of the project's communication and dissemination strategy, as well as a tool for work for the partners.

The PERSEUS Website - Landing Page

1.1 Functions of the project Website

The PERSEUS Website is the first port of call for anyone wanting to know more about the project. At the same time, it is also PERSEUS's own visiting card, so to speak. Other important features of the Website are:

- its usefulness for journalists and media people, who can download press kits and photos;
- its educational function, thanks to pages devoted to selected bibliography and common-language explanations;
- further to this, its operational function as an online point-of-access to all of the project's Open Access output: research papers, documents, open data;
- its blog/news feature, which acts as the very first publishing outlet for news about PERSEUS, which will then be re-posted to social media.

Due to this multitude of needs, the Website was conceived and designed based on criteria of clarity, functionality, simplicity, and beauty. Everything is intended to drive the user's attention towards the main function of the Website: to provide information about the PERSEUS project, its activities, progress, and achievements.

Since the Internet has become a mostly mobile medium, the Website was conceived from the outset to be smartphone- and tablet-compatible. This is why we adopted a responsive Web design solution, i.e. *"...a Web design approach aimed at crafting sites to provide an optimal viewing experience – easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling - across a wide range of devices (from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones)"* (Wikipedia).

Having said so, given its intended target audiences (which comprise science buffs and schools, other fellow scientists, and journalists - see next chapter), the main scenario of use of PERSEUS's Website is via desktop browser.

The PERSEUS Website is W3C compliant.

The PERSEUS Website is conceived for both desktop and mobile use

1.2 Structure and layout based on target users

The Website structure and the design of its graphical user interface were conceived bearing in mind the main scenarios of use and the resulting ‘user trajectories’ from the moment users land on the home page until they reach the information they seek. Model readers thus considered include the following three macro categories: users interested in knowing more about the project (including schools), scientists managers and admins working in scientific research, journalists.

For the latter two groups, the logical layout of the main navigation bar and the deliberately shallow nature of the page tree result in the fastest possible path from landing on the home page to retrieving the desired information. On the other hand, users who are just generally curious are invited to dwell on the rich, high-resolution photos and scientific imagery on which the design is based. Striking visuals are one of the key features of the PERSEUS Website and of the PERSEUS communication strategy in general. They are the easiest way to begin communicating and generating interest in advanced science, not only amongst professionals but also, crucially, within the general public. Besides this, all modern media channels -including social media such as Instagram, Facebook, but also messaging platforms such as Whatsapp, Signal, Snapchat- are mostly or even exclusively image-centric.

A limited colour palette of red, white, and black was employed throughout. This is due to several reasons: primarily, to make the Website stand out in the hyper-crowded and multicoloured landscape of the Web; but also, in order to make the few colour elements within it stand out, which is especially useful for highlighting items of great importance - such as the EU flag.

As a deliberate choice, the Website tends to eschew animations in favour of moveable slides revealing significant images produced by QED or by the research activities connected to PERSEUS. This choice confers an active role to the user.

The Website structure and content will evolve in time according to the needs of the project and of its partners.

1.3 Landing page

The landing (home) page of the Website is a clean-looking and intuitive access point from which all further navigation ensues.

It features large backgrounds derived from the custom photographic campaign that was undertaken as part of the PERSEUS Graphic Identity study (see D5.2 - Project Logo). These attest to the variety of techniques and phenomena underlying PERSEUS. The landing page also features the custom-made photographic portraits of the Project researchers and staff in general - as part of the overall design drive to show the community spirit behind PERSEUS, as part of the overall design philosophy outlined in D5.2 - Project Logo.

In the upper portion of the landing page is the main navigation bar. At the bottom of the page the user will find a contact email address, links to the project’s social media profiles, the EU flag and the caption acknowledging EU funding, as well as match funding from UKRI for the UK partner.

2.4 The main navigation bar

The horizontal navigation bar features the following links (NB: the texts for each of the following subpages are given in Annex 1):

[PERSEUS Logo button]

A button for getting back to the home page, which immediately provides all the essential information about the project, featuring the following paragraphs:

What is PERSEUS?

A summary of the overall mission and activities past and future of the project, which will be updated as PERSEUS progresses.

PERSEUS Website - What is PERSEUS? section

People

The People section was set up in order to offer details of the project staff (photos, bios, recently-completed projects).

PERSEUS Website - People section

The PERSEUS Consortium

A brief description of the PERSEUS Partners, with links to their respective websites.

Project structure

A PERT-chart like graph summarising the work package structure and dependencies of the Project.

PERSEUS Website - Project structure

Science

The Science section provides information on the scientific background of the project, starting from the photos of the various fabrication and characterisation apparatuses taken as part of the Graphic Identity study.

News

The News page is both simple and striking, providing a strong image-based choice of items, each of which can be clicked for further information. This section will be further enriched in the future.

It provides news about the project in a standard, easy-to-read format. It is strongly connected with the social networking environment, i.e. News items are also posted in PERSEUS's social media channels, and, conversely, links to follow PERSEUS's social media profiles are provided. This is a critical step towards successful dissemination and community engagement in this technological age. As far as possible, images will be employed to communicate each entry.

This section will feature news and events that are relevant for the PERSEUS community, including diary-like updates about PERSEUS progress, notices of events organised by PERSEUS, of events organised by other institutions, of projects that have invited PERSEUS partners to promote the its activities, and of other events of interest for the PERSEUS community and target users.

PERSEUS Website - News page

2 TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The Content Management System that has been selected as the base technology for the PERSEUS Website is WordPress - a free, open-source blog tool and publishing platform licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL). WordPress is powered by PHP and MySQL and can easily be customised into a Content Management System (CMS). It has been selected as the base technology for the implementation of the PERSEUS Website because of its flexibility, its user-friendly setup and usage, and its provision of a high level of personalisation. Moreover, its widespread availability has spawned a rich ecosystem of plug-ins, which allow users and developers to extend its functionality beyond the features that come with the base installation. This ensemble of qualities makes WordPress the ideal facilitator of a versatile CMS. Moreover, since it is available for free, it represents maximum value for money.

WordPress has a Web template system that uses a template processor. The processor makes it easy to re-arrange widgets and install and switch between themes. The PHP and HTML code used by the themes can also be edited for more advanced customisations.

WordPress has a number of useful features, which include integrated link management, a search-engine-friendly, clean permalink structure; the ability to assign nested, multiple categories

for articles; support for tagging of posts and articles. Automatic filters are also included, providing standardised formatting and styling of text within articles.

Multimedia files such as images, videos, animations, image galleries, slideshows, etc. can be uploaded and linked to (or displayed in) pages and articles, or embedded directly from other places (e.g. YouTube).

WordPress provides several ready-to-use options for the display of website archives. They can be arranged according to year, month, week, day, category, or author. New archives can be created and easily linked. Since WordPress generates pages dynamically, all these archive pages come at no additional space-cost to the server.

WordPress' built-in search functionality allows visitors to the Website to search for terms they are interested in; the search terms are highlighted, making it even easier for them to find what they were looking for.

WordPress supports the Trackback and Pingback standards for displaying links to other sites that have themselves been linked to a post or article.

Hosting was arranged externally, using value-for-money criteria and a tried-and-trusted provider.

3 SERVICES

3.1 Social network integration

The PERSEUS Website allows for easy, one-click sharing, bookmarking, and emailing of articles and pages through the provision of a large variety of services.

Authorised users can manually post information about events or other relevant information related to the project or partners, as well as select content proposed by the partners. QED is responsible for managing the social network pages.

3.2 Website statistics

Website usage is monitored through Google Analytics, a very popular Web analytics solution that provides many insights into one's website traffic and marketing effectiveness. It allows for Advanced Segmentation, Custom Reports, Advanced Analysis Tools, Analytics Intelligence, Custom Variables, and Data exports¹.

Google Analytics can track visitors from all referrers, including search engines, display advertising, pay-per-click networks, email marketing, and digital 'collateral' such as links within PDF documents.

The service offers the following specific statistical insights:

- number of visits and number of unique visitors
- visit duration and last visits
- domains/countries of visitors
- host list, last visits and unresolved IP addresses list, most viewed, entry and exit

¹ For individual features, see <https://marketingplatform.google.com/about/>

- pages
- browsers used
- robot visits
- search engines, keyphrases and keywords used to arrive at site

Statistics are managed by the webmaster; they are analysed on a tri-monthly basis in order to verify trends and variations.

4 CONTENT

4.1 The Editorial Team

The **Editorial Team** is comprised of the following members:

- the Communication and Dissemination Managers (Dr. Luca Marco Carlo Giberti, QED and Dr. Raffaella Santucci, QED) are in charge of deciding overall strategy and monitoring the activities;
- the Communication and Dissemination Executive (Dr. Raffaella Santucci, QED) is in charge of producing, proofreading, checking, and validating the content and publishing the content on the Website.

The content to be published on the Website and on social media, such as images, video snippets, or shared links to other online resources, is provided by all partners; contributions can be sent to the Editorial Team.

4.2 Intellectual property rights

The PERSEUS Project is the sole responsible party for content published on the Website; it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission.

The text of the PERSEUS Web pages is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (by) license². This means that users are free to share (copy, distribute, and transmit), remix (adapt), and make commercial use of the Website's editorial content under the following conditions:

- **Attribution** — Work must be attributed in the manner specified by the author or licensor (but not in any way that suggests that they endorse you or your use of the work)

It must be noted, however, that the rights to images and videos published on the Website are dependent upon the respective attributions of each content provider and may not fall under the above CC licence. Each image has a specific caption with all relevant information.

All other specific contents may be licensed differently according to agreements with single authors.

² <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable describes the work carried out to implement the first release of the Project's Website.

It has to be noted that the current release of this deliverable presents the first stage in the development of the Website. The Website will be continuously and timely updated along the Project's lifetime, and its structure may change to take into account new requirements.

For the duration of the Project's life, the editorial team will continue to:

- constantly update the content of the Website
- publish news and events in a timely fashion
- make project deliverables and other documentation available in a timely fashion.

ANNEX 1: LIST OF THE SECTIONS IN THE FIRST RELEASE OF THE PERSEUS WEBSITE

What is PERSEUS?

PERSEUS is an EU-funded groundbreaking research project, devoted to the pursuit of a novel nanotechnology-based cancer therapy for deep-seated, clinically unmanageable, drug-resistant, and metastatic tumours.

At present, practical use of nanotechnology in clinical cancer care is still in its infancy - its full potential yet to be realised. PERSEUS aims to bridge this gap thanks to a novel therapy based on specially engineered nano-systems, made of multifunctional 2D layered nanocrystals. When activated by X rays, the nanosystems provide an effective multimodal therapy, with minimal or no adverse effects. This novel paradigm uses X-rays from common computed tomography (CT) scanners not to kill cancer cells directly, but to trigger and to image the nanosystems, which in turn locally give rise to non-mutagenic oncolytic mechanisms. These therapeutic effects are the result of the conversion of low-energy CT X-rays into heat, reactive oxygen species, and radiosensitising agents. X-ray irradiation can also induce immunogenic cell death with the exposure or release of neo-antigens to trigger an anti-cancer immune response.

The use of X-rays makes it possible to reach deep-seated tumours that are inaccessible by visible or near-infrared light-based therapies. In other words, CT radiation is the spark that lights the match. This is a radical vision for an ambitious and high-risk project.

PERSEUS targets a range of cancer types, including metastatic triple negative breast cancer, hepatocellular carcinoma, colorectal cancer, pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma. The nanosystems are biocompatible and also totally inactive in the absence of CT radiation: nanosystems only become active where the CT beam is delivered - hence minimising side effects at distal sites. The therapy is agnostic to the type of cancer and to gender incidence, because it isn't affected by the body's biochemistry. This is a second change of paradigm.

PERSEUS is pursued by a multidisciplinary team composed of physicists, chemists, chemical engineers, biologists, physicians, pharmacologists, and radiologists, all working together to develop an innovative nanotechnological approach to address unmet clinical needs.

People

[Featuring photographic portraits of the researchers and staff working on PERSEUS]

The PERSEUS Consortium

Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche - Italy (Coordinator)

Karolinska Institutet - Sweden

Technion - Israel Institute Of Technology - Israel

Universidad De Vigo - Spain

Wigner Fizikai Kutatokozept - Hungary

BeDimensional Spa - Italy

QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - United Kingdom

The Consortium, composed of world-leading experts across various disciplines, is designed to achieve project goals efficiently and maximise scientific and societal impact. The diverse, geographically widespread team

brings together experts in chemistry, biology, pharmacology, medicine, material science, toxicology, clinical medicine, physics, and chemical engineering in order to safely develop a cutting-edge nanotechnology-based cancer treatment. The team includes renowned scientific institutions, a novel, 2D-materials focused enterprise, BeD, and a dynamic media company, QED. Together, these institutions possess the interdisciplinary know-how and resources to achieve groundbreaking results.

Project structure

Contact and EU Funding

info@perseusproject.eu

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ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	Italy (Coordinator)	CNR
Karolinska Institutet	Sweden	KI
Technion - Israel Institute Of Technology	Israel	TECHNION
Universidad De Vigo	Spain	UVIGO
Wigner Fizikai Kutatokozpont	Hungary	Wigner RCP
BeDimensional Spa	Italy	BEDIMENSIONAL SPA
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.	United Kingdom	QED

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL